

"Enterprise Architecture: A Comprehensive Survey of Frameworks, Tools, and Challenges for Organizational Alignment"

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Abstract

Many organizations worldwide have started their businesses in unscientific basis. This is true for some extent that they are losing time, money, and efforts in adopting project which they realize that these project do not benefit their business unless the face the failure of these projects. Additionally, most of the time they buy many equipment and they only utilize far less than what these equipment can provide. Therefore, many minds worldwide of different specialties and experiences have collaborated together in studying and standardizing the related aspects of organizing businesses in scientific way. They resulted in introducing a new field named EA (Enterprise Architecture) which is responsible of all aspects related to the architecting of the organizations' business, applications, data, and technology. EA will control the flow of undertaken projects toward the pre-defined directions of the organization's vision, strategies, and objectives.

EA field has attracted the attention of many organizations even the small ones because it helps them in the architecting their business in more scientific, efficient, and scalable manner. This significant importance of EA has made many professionals start searching and looking for it. There are many resources that help in understanding the concepts of EA but they lack of presenting clear idea of the overall EA picture. Therefore, providing a comprehensive survey that cover the most important aspects of EA for new joiners either professionals or organizations is the main reason of writing this survey study.

This study has spotted the light on the basic aspects of EA field including: definition, place in management process, reasons of conducting EA, outcomes, history, main institutions that helped in the evolution of EA, certifications, different frameworks, tools, EA maturity measuring, challenges, and the relationship between EA and the entrepreneurship.

Introduction

Governments, Organizations, and Firms (GOFs) are incurring a lot of efforts, time, and money in constructing their IT infrastructure for their facilities. Most of times, this construction is built in rush and it exceeds the real needs that shall serve the businesses. As a result of such losses, many GOFs seek to study and analyze the reasons behind such situations. Also, they look forward to adopting any useful approach that will help them in performing their business in more efficient and time/cost effective way in the future.

GOFs have realized with the help of the scientific studies and experts that they adopt new initiatives especially IT project most of the time without any clear basis and whether these project will benefit their overall vision and goals or not. In addition, some of the GOFs acquire and buy the latest technology and powerful equipment such as servers while they do not utilize them fully. Which result in high waste of time and money in maintenance contracts. All this occur because there was no accurate assessment of their actual needs.

Developing a robust approach that design and manage all the different businesses requirements is not an easy task or a product of individual work. Therefore, a scientific field by itself has been established and named as Enterprise Architecture (EA). The main concern of this field is to standardize all the aspects in regards to two main parts of any organization which are listed as follows:

- **Business:** defining all aspects regarding people & organization, processes & procedures, terminologies and standards.
- **Information Technology (IT):** defining and designing all aspects regarding applications, systems, data, systems behavior, and standards.

In simple words, EA is trying to first grasp the overall enterprise vision, mission, and strategies. Second, analyzing and documenting the current practiced business processes and procedures. Third, examining these processes to total quality principles and exploring improvements and reengineering possibilities that can save some time, costs and efforts. Last, designing and modeling IT infrastructure including applications, systems, data, and systems behavior driven from the pre-defined business goals and objectives and only adopting IT technologies that serve to achieve those goals.

The reason behind conducting this survey paper is due the high importance of EA nowadays especially in the Middle East. Interested beginners are facing difficulties

in finding a full and comprehensive overview of EA. Therefore, this survey paper will provide them the starting point in the EA field.

This survey paper is structured to answer some key questions and to explore the basic knowledge about EA as follows. Section 1, is an overview of EA definitions and basic terminologies. Section 2, elaborates where the enterprise architecture fits in the overall management process. Section 3, gives some important reasons that show why EA is highly significant to an enterprise. Section 4, discusses the main EA outcomes after conducting it. Section 5, presents an overview of the EA history and evolution. Section 6, presents the institute for enterprise architecture developments and in its role in EA field. Section 7, provides clear picture for EA certification for new joiners in the field. Section 8, explains the definition of EA frameworks. Section 9, an overview of some EA frameworks is elaborated. Section 10, a comparison between highly used EA frameworks is elaborated. Section 11, explores some useful EA tools. Section 12, new concept of EA called maturity is explained. Section 13, latest EA challenges are listed. Section 14, presents the relationship between EA and Entrepreneurship. At last, a conclusion that summarizes the survey paper is shown.

Section 1: What is Enterprise Architecture?

There are many definitions for enterprise architecture. The formal definition states “EA is a conceptual blueprint that defines the structure and operation of an organization. The intent of an enterprise architecture is to determine how an organization can most effectively achieve its current and future objectives”. [2]

Gartner definition of EA also states that EA “is a discipline for proactively and holistically leading enterprise responses to disruptive forces by identifying and analyzing the execution of change toward desired business vision and outcomes. EA delivers value by presenting business and IT leaders with signature-ready recommendations for adjusting policies and projects to achieve target business outcomes that capitalize on relevant business disruptions”. [3]

From our experiences and understanding of enterprise architecture we came up with the following practical definition of EA and it states that EA is the analysis & design (derived from the enterprise strategy vision and goals) that integrates people & resources with discipline and develop a way of working for the business which takes into consideration the cohesiveness between products, processes, information and technology infrastructure.

In simple words, EA is all about how to have an efficient and robust harmonization between an enterprise strategy, business and technology. EA will identify and model all details in regards to the three main umbrellas of an enterprise which are the strategy, the business and the technology. The following points describe what EA is detailing for the three umbrellas of EA in general:

- **In regards to Strategy:** EA identifies and formulates the enterprise strategy, goals and objectives. In other words, it defines what to do? And how to do it?
- **In regards to business:** EA identifies business processes for both core business competency such as manufacturing processes or supply chain and support business units such as finance and human resource.
- **In regards to technology:** EA separate this aspect into three detailed sub-aspects as follows:
 - **Application and Systems:** EA identifies the needed applications or IT systems to support both core business competencies and support business units.

- **Information and Data:** EA identifies the most important asset of an enterprise that we can consider it as the blood of the enterprise body. Here, data sources, entities and types are all well identified and documented.
- **Networks and Infrastructure:** EA defines the needed infrastructure to support the data and applications technical components such as servers, networks, DBMS, VPNs, security application ...etc.

By having well-defined enterprise architecture, the stakeholders will be able to organize, understand and answer the following questions:

- What are the enterprise overall vision, mission, goals and objectives?
- What is the overall assessment of the current state of the enterprise?
- How the business is running currently? What are the business processes and procedures are followed in order to produce the desired outcomes?
- What are the correlations between these business processes? How they interact together? Who is responsible for doing activities of a business process?
- What kind of information systems and technologies the enterprise needs to fulfill both core and support business functionalities?
- What kind of data will be processed inside the enterprise information systems?
- How the pre-identified data will be translated into information that will help in enterprise decision making?
- What kind of IT infrastructure the enterprise needs to have its information systems running with sufficient availability, performance, scalability, reliability and recoverability?

The enterprise architecture field includes the following common terminologies:

- **Enterprise:** in enterprise architecture context an enterprise can be defines as a set of interrelated organizations that have common goals to benefit each other. The below figure can simplify the meaning:

- **Architect:** is the responsible person of the enterprise architecture undertaken who harmonize the cooperation of all participants and make sure that the EA is well defined and designed.
- **Architecture:** is a set of common definitions and standards that build the blueprint of part of the enterprise. For example an IT infrastructure component can have its own architecture such networks or databases.
- **Architectural artifact:** a tangible outcome of an activity performed for example model, figure, report, or document that support the overall EA description.
- **Architectural description:** the final document of the EA design which includes all the architectural artifacts resulted from the EA activities.
- **Architectural methodology:** a specific step by step approach to solve a certain issue related to the architectural description.
- **Architectural taxonomy:** a method that defines the structural organization and categorization of architectural artifacts.
- **Architecture Models:** a well-designed figure according to the standards to describe a specific part of the architectural description.
- **Policy Makers:** the personnel who defined the internal specific policies of the enterprise and follow the general policies according the host country laws.
- **Governance:** ensuring the full alignment of the enterprise practices with the defined policies and procedures.
- **Business Analyst:** a person or a team who carry the responsibility of analyzing and documenting all aspects of the enterprise's business.
- **Data Architect:** a professional personnel or a team in data technologies aspects who carry the responsibility of analyzing, designing, creating, deploying, and managing data infrastructure of an enterprise.

- **Technical Architect:** a person or a team of professionals who carry the responsibility of adopting and ensuring the IT/Business alignment to benefit the overall business.
- **Business Process:** a series of predefined steps and procedures with all parties involved to completing a business activity.
- **Building Blocks:** is a re-usable functional component defined to meet business needs such as business, IT, or architectural capability component that can be utilized with other building blocks to deliver architectures. For example, customer database, budget control, customer service, call handling ...etc.

Enterprise Architecture Team Members:

An enterprise architecture project will mainly consists of the cooperation of the following basic team members which is led by the enterprise architect:

- **Enterprise Architect**
- **Policy Makers**
- **Business Analyst**
- **Data Architect**
- **Technical Architect**

The following figure is elaborate the structure of this team members:

The figure shows that the enterprise architect is leader were all other team members are reporting directly to him/her. This comes from the big responsibilities he/she should carry out which include the following general activities:

- Exploring the current state of the overall enterprise business, especially the IT infrastructure components and running information systems. During this exploration he/she should be able to know what technologies are used? How they serve the business requirements? How the IT professionals are working and their structure organization?
- Keeping a record of all current enterprise under development projects especially the IT projects.
- Recording and keep in mind the enterprise future state.
- Applying gap analysis between the current state and the future sate of the enterprise.
- Planning and prioritizing the needed projects which will direct the enterprise to its desired future state.

There are 9 basic steps to conduct a successful EA project in an enterprise as follows:

- Support the EA project with commitment of executive sponsor.
- Recruit high experienced EA architect to lead the project.
- Initiate the EA project inside the enterprise and acquire the commitment of collaboration of all parties.
- Plan the EA project composition which includes the EA project scope and the EA framework to be used for completing the project.
- Form the EA team members internally (subject domain experts) and externally (consultants).
- Acquire all the EA needed resources such as funds, time, and software tools that help in EA documentation and modeling activities.
- Assign the tasks and activities to the EA team members.
- Provide training as needed.
- Complete all EA project activities.

These steps can be viewed as EA practical lifecycle shown in the figure below:

Figure ...

This is a practical lifecycle that describes the overall activities required to start and complete EA project successfully. As part of this practical lifecycle the following is an important guidelines that help is EA success from the enterprise personnel perspective:

- Require formal detailed performance documentation regularly.
- Have performance failure meetings to seek issues and solutions.
- Do not personalize meetings keep them professional.
- Fulfill all required resource on time to get the desired results on time.
- Be honest in presenting the real picture about the enterprise do not hide or decorate facts.

Section 2: Where does EA fit in the enterprise Management Process?

A widely spread management process pyramid “Strategy pyramid business management process” is well known by GOFs. The pyramid starts at the top with vision followed by mission then goals, strategies, tactics, and the pyramid base is the action plans (Figure ..).

To make it clear to the management of the enterprise below we define that EA can fit in the management process pyramid as follows:

The EA plays a critical role in first understanding the overall business vision, mission strategy, and the current state goals along with the future state. In addition, it has a significant role in transforming the business goals into day-to-day operations that are improved as much as possible. EA does work alone in the enterprise overall business management processes. It works with cooperation and high integration with other management standards or frameworks such as IT governance, IT service delivery, total quality management, and balanced scorecards.

Section 3: Why Enterprise Architecture?

Governments, Organizations and Firms tend to initiate an undertaken endeavor to design and architect their enterprise. They start this project knowing that it will require and consume lots of time, money and resources. So, why they end up doing it? Doing EA in enterprises have various reasons as follows:

Complexity of business and systems

GOFs have sometimes very complex business processes and information systems depend on how large they are. The complexity is even increases according to the growth rate, incomes, production lines, target markets, branches and customers. If such complexity is not well defined and controlled in a changeable manner, the owners will lose many resources in terms of time, money and efforts.

Uncertainty of Enterprise Information

Many enterprises have multiple information systems running in different business units with some sort of integration. Different information systems by nature and design requirements have different data structures for example financial and accounting systems have different design and requirements from human resource systems. Such information system planning can produce data redundancy, inconsistency and integrity issues especially if they have different data infrastructures and database types. On that basis, managers will have always some sort of suspicion on the reports generated which they mainly depend when making decisions. Therefore, EA is made to discover these kinds of information uncertainty, assess its negative impacts on the overall enterprise and suggest solutions for this problem.

Lack of on-time of Enterprise Information

Integration between different information systems produces untimely reporting of information. There are lots of downloads and uploads have to take place between integrated systems through their interfaces to do the required functionalities and therefore produces the needed reports for managers for decision making. Sometimes there are some human interventions to accomplish such integration activities between systems or other activities that are operated manually. In fact, decision making is highly depend on having the right information at the right time. EA can

help to discover these lacks and provide better understanding and utilization of technology to have the right information at the right time.

Development of New Information Systems

Many information systems undertaken by enterprises are tending to failure. This is because of the lack of full documentation of business processes and the understanding of the interrelations between them. This result to a huge waste of time, money and resources of the enterprise and there are cases of which the information system project is completed but no one is using it. Such problems can be avoided by having well-designed EA which will help IT departments to understand the business needs and the information systems needed to fulfill these needs before starting the implementation activities.

Organizations Partnerships

There are many cases where organizations are having some sort of partnerships for example a manufacturing company with the raw materials suppliers. Of course, each organization of those is running their own information systems and business processes in isolation and it is difficult to merge them together. Therefore, EA may help in understanding the linkage points between these partners and design how business process and information systems components might be integrated which will save time and money for both organizations.

Autonomous Enterprise business units

The enterprise value will be highly increased if it has some parts of the business units are running autonomously. This will help the enterprise is offering such units for sale because they will be easily excluded with minimal and pre-defined losses.

Core Business versus Support Business Competencies

Recently, GOFs tend to concentrate more in their core business competencies and outsource other support business functionalities. EA will give a clear picture and differentiation between the enterprise core and support business functions as well as the outsourcing opportunities.

Customers Relationships Automation

Nowadays, customers want to inspect the products or services, place orders, check the delivery status and complete the payments processes online. EA will provide the

enterprise clear vision about how customers might access the information system without breaching the security regulations.

IT versus Business Groups Alignment

There are huge gaps between IT and business professionals for many years. On one side, IT sees that business is not following the standards as well as not having clear view of the own requirements. While on the other side, business sees IT is not having the sufficient capabilities for delivering the required functionalities. Therefore, EA can gather both IT and business together in one round table to discuss and plan how to have maximum alignment between IT and business.

Continuous Requirements Changing

It common in business and life in general that requirement keeps changing by the rapid evolving of technology and customer needs. Therefore, having a robust requirements change management mechanisms and planning and building the enterprise information system in a way that they are welcome to change is what EA is all about.

Managing IT systems

Managing IT systems and delivering the products and services to the concerned beneficiary is one the key success factors in an enterprise success. Moreover, acquiring new technologies or new information systems is one of the enterprises challenges. Thus, EA is the preliminary of understanding how IT systems are interrelated with each other. Also, it provide smooth planning and managing if IT systems.

Communication with stakeholders

Miscommunication between stakeholders and managing them is one of the challenges that each enterprise is facing. EA is providing a strong mechanism for identifying, classifying them into groups and determining their management approach.

Innovation

GOFs are always seeking new innovative ideas and opportunities to keep improving their products and services. However, innovation can only be triggered when an enterprise has full understanding and documented structures regarding its

businesses. Therefore, EA is providing full and well-designed structures about the enterprise that will be a goldmine of innovative ideas.

Governance

Keep complaint with governance regulations is the only way that avoid an enterprise falling in troubles. EA is emphasizing of the governance regulations and put them into considerations in every aspect of the business. Moreover, EA ensures that governance policies are implemented in the information systems with the ability of modifying the systems in case of changing policies.

Documentation and Modeling

EA is mainly focusing on having every aspect of the enterprise documented. It is also elaborating many aspects through standard modeling notations to visualize for example business organization hierarchy; business processes workflows and information systems infrastructure.

Future State

EA is clearly drawing the desired future state of the enterprise. It also formulates the road map that will enable the enterprise to keep inline in order to reach its goals.

Having all that in mind, enterprise architecture can provide the following values:

- Understand the strategy, the business, the systems and the infrastructure and their correlations
- Know how the enterprise assets (physical, funds, people ...etc.) resources will cooperate to achieve the goals
- View information & data in way that helps in decision making and do the right things at the right time
- Prioritize things and know what to do first and next according to the available resources & capabilities
- Govern and Manage changes according to the policies and laws (Do the things right).

Section 4: What are the Enterprise Architecture outcomes?

It is very difficult to convince an enterprise top management to conduct an enterprise architecture initiative unless they see clearly the final outcomes and the return on investment (ROI). The following list includes some of the valuable EA outcomes:

- Ensuring that all IT projects and information systems are derived from the business strategic goals and help in achieving them.
- Having maximum utilization of IT resources which will increase the overall business performance.
- Satisfying the top management desire in having well justified and prioritized IT initiatives according to their criticality to the business and within the available funds and resources.
- Harmonizing and having the required integration between IT components such as networks, servers, services, databases and information systems throughout all the enterprise.
- Achieving full transparency through the easy sharing of information between different business units or lines.
- Decreasing the costs of duplications of IT resources inside the different business units of the enterprise.
- Having best practices of securing data and IT components assets.
- Having strong control for IT professional personnel knowledge and skills.
- Having clear understanding and documented modeling of the enterprise current state including process and information models supported by analysis of issues and risks.
- Having clear understanding and documented modeling of the enterprise future state and changes including reengineered process and information models.
- Having clear enterprise core diagram which include a list of systems and processes that considered as the core operations of the enterprise.
- Having a clear enterprise capability model supported by capability gap analysis of the desired future state.
- Having a clear enterprise Governance model that clarify ensure that all enterprise practices are in line with the predefined policies and procedures.

Section 5: History of Enterprise Architecture?

Enterprise Architecture is not a new field. It has started in late 60s and still evolving day after day. The following shows briefly the chronological order of the enterprise architecture evolving over time:

- In late 1960s, business systems planning (BSP) Dewey Walker defined architecture.
- In 1980s, Walker's student named John Zachman has contributed in enhancing the BSP.
- In mid 1980s, John Zachman has introduced to the field his own structured enterprise architecture framework.
- In 1989, Department of Defense Architecture Framework (DoDAF) and Treasury Enterprise Architecture Framework (TEAF) have been developed by the concerned federal entities.
- In 1992, Enterprise Architecture Planning (EAP) has been added to the field of enterprise architecture.
- In 1994, architecture named Uniform Visualization Architecture UVA Model is presented into enterprise architecture field.
- In 1995, The Open Group Organization has developed its first version of enterprise architecture framework called The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF).
- In 1996, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) organization has formulated International Standards Organization/International Electro technical Commission (ISO/IEC 14252).
- In 1996 also, Integrated Architecture Framework (IAF v1) was presented as an enterprise architecture.
- In 1997, Treasury Information System Architecture Framework (TISAF) has been developed.
- In 1999, the federal CIO Council of United States of America has developed what so called Federal Enterprise Architecture Framework (FEAF) that developed to design and plan the enterprise of a federal government.
- In 1999 also, what so called Command, Control, Communications, Computers, Intelligence, Surveillance, Target Acquisition and Reconnaissance (C4ISR) has been introduced.

- In 2003, Extensible Architecture Framework (XAF) was also presented in the field of enterprise architecture.
- In 2005, one of the top information technology research and advisory firms named (Gartner) have developed what so called Gartner Enterprise Architecture Framework (GEAF).
- In 2005 onwards, Common Information Model Open System Architecture (CIMOSA), Purdue Enterprise Reference Architecture (PERA), Standards and Architectures for eGovernment Applications (SAGA) and Generalized Enterprise Reference Architecture (GERAM) are all enterprise architectures that were developed and introduced in the field.

All these architecture frameworks have continuous improvements over time and referenced with various versions. For example, one of the most common enterprise architecture nowadays is TOGAF version 9.1 which was emerged in 2009. It is also worth mentioning that some companies have conceptualized their own enterprise architecture for example Oracle Company has developed what they called The Oracle Enterprise Architecture Framework (OEAF) in 2009.

All those architecture frameworks have common understanding to the fact of all enterprise's information system, applications, data, information and IT infrastructure should be derived after having clear picture and modeling of the business vision, mission, goals and objectives. In contrast, each architecture framework of these has different look in investigating and designing the architecture. For example, they differ in the sequential order of the steps, the techniques and tools that will formulate the architecture blueprint.

Section 6: What is Institute For Enterprise Architecture Developments (IFAED)?

Institute For Enterprise Architecture Developments

Your, Return On Information

<http://www.enterprise-architecture.info>

About IFEAD

It is considered as one of the important sources of knowledge regarding the Enterprise Architecture and its future in cooperation with many research centers and universities. It is responsible for providing information regarding enterprise architecture to support the enterprise architects including standards, methodologies, tools, best-practices, and latest news to serve the Enterprise Architecture community and these are the main goals and objectives.

About the Founder

Jaap Schekkerman has founded IFEAD in 2001. He received degrees in clinical chemistry, electronic engineering, and certifications in information technology and business economics. He has many publications in EA.

Partnerships

IFEAD has many collaborative partners at different levels shown in the table below:

Exchange Partnership	
Center for the Advancement of the Enterprise Architecture Profession www.caeap.org	
Enterprise Architecture Solutions www.silofx.com	

<p>Global Enterprise Architecture Organization www.geao.org</p>	
<p>UnternehmensArchitektur www.unternehmensarchitektur.de</p>	
<p>World-Wide Institute of Software Architects www.wwisa.org</p>	
<p>Intervista Institute www.intervista-institute.com</p>	
<p>Federated Enterprise Architecture Certification Institute www.feacinstitute.org</p>	
<p>Publishing Partnership</p>	
<p>International Association of Enterprise Architects www.aeajournal.org</p>	
<p>Enterprise Architecture Community www.eacommunity.com</p>	
<p>Research Partnership</p>	
<p>bITa Center www.bit-a-center.com</p>	
<p>Zachman International www.zachmaninternational.com</p>	

Section 7: Enterprise Architecture Certification

The following figure illustrates the basic architects' terminologies and certifications levels:

As clearly seen from the figure, there are two major levels:

- **Architecture:** as a general term the professional is called as System Architect. This professional might be specialized in different contexts like Enterprise, Business, IT or Software. Each context has its own certifications to be:
 - **Enterprise Architect**
 - **Business Architect**
 - **IT Architect**
- **Design:** as a general term the professional is called as System Designer where the focus is on technology oriented with detailed and narrowed scope. This professional might be specialized in different system components like:
 - **Networking**
 - **Databases**
 - **Operating systems**
 - **Programming Languages**

For EA certifications there are many institutes as shown in the tables below:

Certified Enterprise Architect (CEA)

Provided by

<http://www.feac institute.org/>

It provides the certification through practice. That means they let the participant to get involved in real projects and learning education in three different EA frameworks FEA Federal Enterprise Architecture, DOD Department of Defense Architecture, and CEA Commercial Enterprise Architecture

Master of Enterprise Architecture

Provided by

<http://www.rmit.edu.au/csit/enterprise>

It provides a Master degree of technology (EA) which is a high-level coursework program designed especially for ICT (Information and Communications Technology) professionals.

IT Architect Certification Program

Provided by

<http://www.opengroup.org/itac/>

It provides the certification by demonstrating skills, experiences, and success in architecting using the EA framework TOGAF.

The USA Chief Information Officer Certificate Program

Provided by

<http://www.ndu.edu/irmc/programs/cio.html>

It provides the certification after completing eleven subject areas of CIO competency.

For Software Architects or System Designers certifications there are many vendors as shown in the tables below:

Vendors Certification

Cisco Certification, CompTIA (Computing Technology Industry Association) Certification, IBM Certification, SUN Java Certification, Microsoft Certification, Red Hat Linux ...etc.

The following are examples of such certifications:

In Networking: Cisco CCNA, CCDA, CCNP, CCIE ... etc.

In CompTIA: A+, Server+, Linux+, ITProject+, e-Biz+ ... etc.

In Microsoft technologies: MCP, MCP+Internet, MCSE, MCSE+Internet ... etc.

Section 8: What is Enterprise Architecture Framework?

The formal definition of EAF states, “EAF defines how to create and use an enterprise architecture. An architecture framework provides principles and practices for creating and using the architecture description of a system”.

In our words, we can define an enterprise architecture framework as a set of structures that provides method to design an enterprise vision as set of building blocks and their relations and provides recommended standards & tools for the implementation of the pre-defined enterprise building blocks.

As seen from the history section, there many EAF developed by the global collaboration of many experts and entities in order to reach the desired simple state and to make the EA conducting as clear as possible. This survey paper will present the main concepts in general of the following EA frameworks:

- **Zachman**
- **Gartner**
- **Integrated Architecture Framework**
- **Department of Defense Architecture Framework (DoDAF)**
- **Control, Communications, Computers, Intelligence, Surveillance, Target Acquisition and Reconnaissance (C4ISR)**
- **Extended Enterprise Architecture Framework (E2AF)**
- **Computer Integrated Manufacturing Open Systems Architecture (CIMOSA)**
- **The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF)**
- **Federal Enterprise Architecture Framework (FEAF)**
- **Treasury Enterprise Architecture Framework (TEAF)**
- **Oracle Enterprise Architecture Framework (OEAF)**

The paper will mainly focus in details in regards to four highly used EAF which are:

- **Zachman**
- **The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF)**
- **Federal Enterprise Architecture Framework (FEAF)**
- **Gartner**

Section 9: Overview of some Enterprise Architecture Frameworks

Zachman

The formal definition of this framework is “a logical structure for classifying and organizing the descriptive representations of an Enterprise that are significant to the management of the Enterprise, as well as the development of the Enterprise’s systems”. In other words, Zachman framework is a taxonomy which means the overall organizational classification structure and the enterprise’s system development.

It works in a table format where the rows represents different descriptions about the enterprise form different perspectives as follows:

- **Contextual (Scope):** many lists of things important to business including: list of data, list of business processes, list of locations where the processes run, list of people or roles that perform the processes, list of times triggering events that define when the processes or activities have to start, and the list of goals that considered as the motivation of the performing the processes.
- **Conceptual (Enterprise Model):** many technology-neutral figures and models that visualize the contextual lists in general and understandable for non-technical experts. For example, semantic, business process, logistics networks, work flows, time schedules, and business plans models.
- **Logical (System Model):** many figures and models that represents the overall system architecture for the contextual lists. For example, logical data, application architecture, distributed systems architecture, human interface architecture, processing structure, and business rules models.
- **Physical (Technology Model):** high level representations that show the technology constraints. For example, physical data, system design, technical architecture, presentation architecture, control structure, and rule design models.
- **Out-of-Context (Detailed Model):** low level detailed representations and models. For example, data definitions, programs, network architecture, security architecture, timing definition, and rule specifications.

The columns in Zachman architecture is the different perspectives that the rows are describing:

- **Data**
- **Function**
- **Network**
- **People**
- **Time**
- **Motivation**

Gartner

It defines the enterprise architecture by combining and strengthening the relationships of three main viewpoints: business, information, and technology. Simply Gartner Enterprise Architecture Framework (GEAF) process model is working as follows:

- **Documenting the enterprise current state**
- **Architecting the enterprise future state:** through the development of the enterprise requirements, principles, and models.
- **Filling the gaps between the current and the future states:** without breaching the policies and with fully alignment of the governance guidelines.

Integrated Architecture Framework

It is very similar to Zachman as it works in 4X4 tabular format where the columns (Aspect Areas) represents the following:

- **Business**
- **Information**
- **Information Systems**
- **Information Infrastructure**

While the rows (Abstract Levels) are trying to answer some key questions and describe the above aspect areas as follows:

- **Contextual Level:** answers why the business exists? By defining the goals, concepts, and drivers for the business area. For the information area,

it answers why the business performs its activities. For information system area, it answers why the system exists by defining the system goals, concepts, and drivers. For technology infrastructure, it answers why the infrastructure exists by defining the goals, concepts, and drivers.

- **Conceptual Level:** answers what are the levels of business collaboration, levels of information interaction, levels of information systems interoperability, and levels of technology infrastructure inter-connectivity.
- **Logical Level:** answers how the business collaboration, information interaction, information systems interoperability and technology infrastructure inter-connectivity are planned to be handled.
- **Physical Level:** answers with what kind of solutions the aspect areas are going to operate.
- **Transformation Level:** answers when in terms of timeframes and conditions that the changes in the aspect areas should be handled.

Department of Defense Architecture Framework (DoDAF)

It is one of the most complex EA frameworks. Here is a summarized overview of how it works. DoDAF is building the EA by analyzing three different but interrelated views shown in the following figure:

Control, Communications, Computers, Intelligence, Surveillance, Target Acquisition and Reconnaissance (C4ISR)

Another complex framework just like DoDAF. The purpose of this framework is improving the countries departments of defense capabilities and make them ready to “Go to War” at any time in terms of requirements planning readiness. This framework is focusing in the enhancements and the effective investments that result into effective warriors engineering.

Extended Enterprise Architecture Framework (E2EAF)

This framework has been developed by the IFEAD (Institute For Enterprise Architecture Developments). It works in similar manner of the Integrated Enterprise Architecture.

Computer Integrated Manufacturing Open Systems Architecture (CIMOSA)

This one can be defined as more likely an enterprise system development lifecycle. It works as follows:

- **First**, it defines and model the enterprise as:
 - **Structure**: includes the rules and organizational structure.
 - **Activities**: includes the enterprise information, functions, materials, Resource, and constraints.
- **Second**, it defines the enterprise overall requirements based on the user inputs.
- **Third**, it starts the design which influenced by the enterprise systems constraints. The designs is done in generic building blocks approach.
- **Fourth**, the implementation starts which tries to increase the components reusability and result the inter-connected system components.

The following figure represents the TEAF matrix:

View		Functional	Information	Organizational	Infrastructure
Perspective	Planner	Vision & Mission Statements	Information Dictionary	Organizational Charts	Technical Reference Model Standards Profile
		Activity Model	Conceptual Information Exchange Matrix	Conceptual Node Connectivity Description	Information Assurance Risk Mgt System Interface Description
	Designer	Business process / System Function Matrix Event Trace Diagrams State Charts	Logical Information Exchange Matrix Data CRUD Matrices Logical Data Models	Logical Node Connectivity Description	System Interface Descriptions
		Builder	System Functionality Description	Physical Information Exchange Matrix Physical Data Model	Physical Node Connectivity Description
Essential Work Products			Supporting Work Products		

The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF)

The formal definition of this framework is “a framework for enterprise architecture that provides an approach for designing, planning, implementing, and governing an enterprise information technology architecture”. In more simple words, TOGAF it can be defined as is a set of systematic series of steps and processes to analyze, design and construct EA for an enterprise.

TOGAF has been created by The Open Group Organization which is a vendor and technology neutral organization. It has more than three hundred member organizations from all around the world such as banks, financial services, governments, manufacturing, and retail firms. It is important to know that TOGAF is a result of best practices & knowledge of experts worldwide over thirteen years of development.

TOGAF the overall enterprise architecture into four sub-architectures abbreviated in BAD-T as follows:

- **B**usiness
- **A**pplication

- **Data**
- **Technology**

The following figure illustrate this concept:

TOGAF is an input/output methodology where it required certain seeds in order to result the desired ripe fruits as follows:

- **Inputs:**
 - Business Requirements
 - Business Vision
 - Legacy
 - Business Drivers
 - Governance Strategy & policies
- **Outputs:**

- Business Scenarios
- Programs & Projects
- Architecture Governance
- Architecture Contract
- People, process & technology

The following figure illustrates this input/output concept:

TOGAF has six major components for conducting the enterprise architecture show in the figure below:

ADM (Architecture Development Method)

It is the core of TOGAF. It can be defined as an iterative method consists of nine phases specifically designed to address business requirements from different architecture views (Business, Data, Apps and Technology) represented as circles around the requirements with bidirectional arrows to emphasize that everything is derived and affected by the requirements. The following figure illustrates the core nine phases of TOGAF ADM and their relationships with the four sub-architectures of TOGAF (Business, Application, Data, and Technology).

In fact, the ADM phases can be summarized into only four major phases as follows:

- **Initiating:** start preparing the organization for conducting the EA project and their commitment and involvements which is done in details the preliminary and architecture vision phases.
- **Architecting:** start describing and designing the four sub-architectures which is done in details in the business, information systems, and technology architectures phases.
- **Executing:** start implementing the four sub-architectures and make them working which is done in details in the opportunities and solutions, migration planning, and implementation governance phases.

- **Running:** start running the overall EA of the organization and make sure to resolve the requirement changes according to the pre-defined procedures which is done in details in the architecture change management phase.

The following figure shows how the TOGAF ADM summarization:

Architecture Content Framework

It provides a detailed model of architectural outcomes such as deliverables, artefacts and building blocks. In addition, it includes a description of a Meta model of the building blocks. Whereas, it does not provide (graphical) representations for the building blocks (it is only lists along with descriptions). There are three basic terminologies in architecture content framework as defined below:

- **Deliverable:** the products of projects that are contractually specified, formally reviewed, agreed, signed off by the stakeholders, and archived at

- completion in the Architecture Repository as a reference model. For example, Architecture Principles, Architecture Vision, Capability Assessment, Communications Plan, Architecture Change Request, Requirements Impact Assessment ...etc. out of each phase of ADM phases
- **Artifact:** describes a particular viewpoint of the architectures. It has three main types
 - **Catalogs:** is the list of things & their descriptions. For example, Applications Portfolio or interfaces...etc.
 - **Matrices:** is the interrelations between the things. For example, Business Interaction, Application Interaction, Stakeholder Map...etc.
 - **Diagrams:** is the pictures of the things. For example, Value Chain, Class Diagram, Network Computing-Hardware ...etc.
 - **Building block:** a re-usable functional component defined to meet business needs such as business, IT, or architectural capability component that can be utilized with other building blocks to deliver architectures. For example, customer database, budget control, customer service, call handling ...etc.

The following figure illustrate the relationships between Deliverables, Artifacts, and Building Blocks:

ADM Guidelines & Techniques

This component represents the actual work where all the outcomes desired from the ADM can be resulted. It contains huge number of techniques and executable step by step guidelines that help in describing and designing many aspects in different stages and levels. For example, stakeholder management, gap analysis, architectures patterns, business scenarios, risk assessments, capability based planning, migration planning, business transformation techniques and many others.

Enterprise Continuum

It is an abstract view of all the architecture assets (descriptions, models, building blocks and artifacts) which are available for the development. It is also a classification of the internal and external architectures of the Architecture Repository as follows:

- **Internal architecture and solution artifacts** (e.g. re-usable deliverables)
- **External architecture and solution artifacts** which is classified into:
 - **Generic Foundation Architectures** reference models and architecture patterns named in TOGAF as (Technical Reference Model (TRM)) which is also classified as into:
 - specific to IT aspects (web services architecture)
 - specific to information processing types (e-Commerce, supply chain management)
 - **Organization-Specific Architectures** reference models and architecture patterns to certain industries (e.g. TMF (in the Telecommunications sector), ARTS (Retail), Energistics (Petrotechnical), etc).

There are three types of Enterprise continuum:

- **Enterprise:** classifies assets related to the context of the whole enterprise (policies, standards, strategic initiatives, organizational structures, and enterprise-level capabilities).
- **Architecture:** includes the Generic Foundation and the Organization-Specific.
- **Solutions:** describes the implementation aspects of the things defined in the Architecture Continuum.

Reference Models

There are two major types of TOGAF reference models:

- **(TRM) Technical Reference Models:** considered as a model of organizing the generic platform services.
- **(III-RM) Integrated Information Infrastructure Model:** considered as a model of the business and infrastructure applications.

Architecture Capability Framework

It defines the overall organizational operations levels and practice. It requires having different types of management capabilities such as financial, service, quality, performance, risk, resource, configuration, communication, supplier, and environment. It also responsible to define the organization roles, skills, and responsibilities.

Federal Enterprise Architecture Framework (FEAF)

It helps the governments to apply common approach for planning and organizing its agencies that help in analyzing and controlling investments. It includes a set of reference models that represent six different architecture domains strategy, business, data, applications, infrastructure, and security.

In FEAF the enterprise is classified into:

- **Core mission area segments:** includes education, health, economic development, community and social services, natural resources, and homeland and security.
- **Business services segments:** includes human resources and financial management.
- **Enterprise segments:** includes security and records management.

FEAF has a process that contains four steps as follows:

- **Step 1:** analyze and define vision for each segment.
- **Step 2:** define and develop enterprise architecture for each segment including business, data, and technology architecture.
- **Step 3:** secure the funding for the projects implementations.
- **Step 4:** Plan, execute, and manage the programs and projects.

Treasury Enterprise Architecture Framework (TEAF)

This framework divides the EA into three sections as follows:

- **Views:** represents essential part of the whole enterprise from specific perspective. This framework defines four different types of views:
 - **Functional:** includes all aspects that support the business operations such as processes, procedures, tasks, and activities.
 - **Information:** defines all the types of information that business operations are processing and resulting as well as the interrelationships between them.
 - **Organizational:** defines and model all the organizational structures of the enterprise in terms of locations, roles, responsibilities, authorities and delegations.
 - **Infrastructure:** defines all the technological aspects and models related the designs of networks, telecommunications, hardware, softwares and services.
- **Perspectives:** represents the parts of the architecture that is defined and designed by specific group of the concerned stakeholders of the corresponding view. This framework defines four different types of perspectives:
 - **Planner:** focuses on the strategic planning, key information, KPIs, the structure of the organization and the executing locations.
 - **Owner:** focuses on the conceptual descriptions of the processes, activities, performers and technology infrastructure.
 - **Designer:** focuses on the logical representations, figures and models of the business processes and the overall architecture components.
 - **Builder:** focuses on the actual tools, technologies, and materials that will transform the designs into reality.
- **Work Products:** represent all the outputs and deliverables of the previous mentioned views that are created by the perspectives. For example, vision & mission statements, organizational charts, standards profiles, risk assessment model, system interface ...etc.

Oracle Enterprise Architecture Framework (OEAF)

It is a hybrid framework that combined the many principles of TOGAF, FEA, and Gartner. It includes nine principles, seven components and process of six steps that ensure the agile enterprise architecture design and development for

aligning the business requirements and needs along with the IT implementation practices. The following figure shows the seven components of OEAF:

- **Business Architecture:** defines three major areas about the business:
 - **Business Strategy:** includes the major requirements, objectives, goals, risks, and performance indicators.
 - **Business Function:** includes processes, procedures, activities, services, and capabilities.
 - **Business Organization:** includes the organizational structure, funding information, roles, internal & external stakeholders, and decision making mechanism.
- **Application Architecture:** defines five major areas about the application:
 - **Application Strategy:** what are the organization's principles and guidelines in application development process? For example, outsourced or in-house development, cloud hosting or in-house hosting, open source or closed source.
 - **Application Services:** a warehouse of all the services that help the internal and the external stakeholders.
 - **Application Processes:** a set of special application that participate in accomplishing some business activities or some tasks and activities.
 - **Logical Components:** list or warehouse of the products or components that supports the existence and ensure the operating of the application systems.
 - **Physical Components:** the actual products or components that supports the existence and ensure the operating of the application systems.
- **Information Architecture:** defines two major areas about the information:
 - **Information Strategy:** includes the information governance, data models, and priorities of data according their internal or external owners and levels.
 - **Information Assets:** list of data types and models that represents their relationships with the all the services, processes, and applications.
- **Technology Architecture:** defines four major areas about the technology:
 - **Technology Strategy:** IT governance, portfolio management, and technology standards.
 - **Technology Services:** lists or warehouse of all the technology services that are needed to support the business services, applications, and data assets with models representing their relationships.

- **Logical Components:** list or warehouse of the technology services components that supports the existence and ensure the operating of the application systems or business services.
- **Physical Components:** the actual technology services components that supports the existence and ensure the operating of the application systems or business services.
- **EA Governance:** defines four major areas about the Governance:
 - **People:** individuals and groups who are responsible for the Governance compliance in the organization.
 - **Processes & Policies:** management and lifecycle processes of new undertaken projects, changes or reviews.
 - **Technology:** the organization's IT Governance principles and auditing procedures.
 - **Financial:** the financial Governance principles of funds securing, budget allocations, IT costs, and monitoring the disbursements and ROI.
- **People, Processes, & Tools:**
 - **People:** individuals and groups who are responsible for different architectural development, and maintenance.
 - **Processes:** the way of selecting the set of processes that increase the opportunities of the success of implementations and decrease the potentials of failures.
 - **Tools:** a set of tools that help in conducting the enterprise architecture of different types such as modeling, portfolio management, and architecture repository tools.
- **EA Repository:** is the warehouse were all the outcomes of the enterprise architecture activities are stored, managed, retrieved anytime anywhere including the models, figures, graphs, artifacts, texts, descriptions, principles, lessons learned ... etc.

The following figure shows the six steps of OEAF development process:

Section 10: Comparison between common Enterprise Architecture Frameworks

Each enterprise architecture framework has its own uses, strengths, and weaknesses. This section tries to show a comparison between some common EAFs as follows:

EAF	Strengths	Weaknesses
Zachman	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient and result a completed taxonomy • Powerful in classifications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not include a complete process • Poor practice guidelines • Has no maturity model
TOGAF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information availability • Completed process • Vendor neutral • Technology neutral 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generic • Has no maturity model • Poor in practice guidelines • Does not focus on specific business
FEAF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completed Process • Rich in reference models guidelines • Vendor neutral • Governance Guide 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applied so far for Governments not business • Poor in information availability
Gartner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business focus • Has maturity model • Rich in practice guidelines • Governance Guide 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor in information availability • Poor in reference models availability • Not vendor neutral

Section 11: Enterprise Architecture Frameworks Tools

All EA tools should be able to fulfill the following requirements:

- Developing, storing, presenting, and enhancing the architecting of enterprise architecture.
- Modeling the business strategies, organizational structures, business processes, procedures, tasks, activities, data flows, applications, and technology infrastructures.
- Analyzing, simulating, and optimizing all the previous mentioned models in point 2.

There are many enterprise architecture tools and softwares. Below is a review of the most common ones:

Enterprise Architecture Management

<http://www.alfabet.de/>

It provides a way of understanding and managing the alignment of the business strategies and the IT project portfolio.

Functionalities

- Supports EA design
- Supports EA frameworks & standards such as TOGAF or ArchiMate
- Supports navigation, analysis, and easy access of the EA models
- Supports Architecture governance

Abacus

<http://www.avolution.com.au/products.html>

It provides a powerful way of understanding, analyzing, and modeling enterprise architecture including people, processes, and technology.

Functionalities

- Supports EA design and modeling through for any number of users.
- Support many EA frameworks such as TOGAF, ArchiMate, BPMN, FEAF, DoDAF ... etc.
- Drag and drop functionalities for modeling different artifacts.
- Upload data from Excel, Visio, sharepoint and other resources.
- Open API for customized reports, queries, and scripts.
- Analyzing of major business metrics for example ROI (Return On Investment), TCO (Total Cost of Ownership), and performance.+
- Publishing of dynamic HTML5 dashboards.

BiZZdesign Architect

Powered by

<http://www.bizzdesign.com/>

It provides a full integrated solution called Enterprise Studio for enterprise architecture design and analysis.

Functionalities

- Supports EA design
- Supports Business Process Management
- Supports Portfolio Management
- Supports Business Model and Strategy
- Supports Governance Risks and Compliance
- Supports Business Logic
- Supports Data Management

Casewise Corporate Modeler

Powered by

<http://www.casewise.com/Products/CorporateModelerSuite/>

It provides a way that enables the cooperation between business and IT people to capture the “as-is” business processes and simulating “to-be” situations.

Functionalities

- Supports modeling business processes
- Supports analyzing and suggesting optimizations chances
- Supports simulating of suggested changes
- Supports multi-user functionality

Dragon1 Enterprise Architecture Tool

Powered by

<https://www.dragon1.com/enterprise-architecture-tool>

It provides the EA tool online as a cloud based SaaS (Software as a Service) for modeling and creating animated enterprise architectures.

Functionalities

- Supports Online and social networking environment
- Supports tasks managing, ePortfolio, architecture repository, visual designer, resource center ... etc.
- Supports templates, checklists, and tutorials
- Supports standardization of naming conventions

IBM Rational System Architect

Powered by

<http://www-01.ibm.com/software/awdtools/systemarchitect/>

It provides a way to plan, generate and control data-driven views of the enterprise architecture.

Functionalities

- Supports building of business processes models and simulations
- Supports designing EA using the framework of FEAF
- Supports reverse-engineering and analyzing ERP systems such as SAP

Metastorm

Powered by

<http://www.metastorm.com/>

It is a tool for business process modeling and management.

Functionalities

- Supports Process Intelligence with smart dashboards that help in decision making
- Supports defining business rules

Troux

http://www.troux.com/products/troux_9/

It provides a set of applications for collaboration and modeling of enterprise architecture.

Functionalities

- Supports integration with common CMDB (Configuration Management Database), Asset management, and ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning)
- Supports integration with common IT management frameworks such as COBIT or ITIL
- Supports EA frameworks like TOGAF

ARIS Platform

http://www.softwareag.com/corporate/products/aris_alfabet/bpa/overview/default.asp

It provides a Master degree of technology (EA) which is a high-level coursework program designed especially for ICT (Information and Communications Technology) professionals.

Functionalities

- Supports sharing and working in collaboration with stakeholders using role based process portal
- Supports integration with ERP systems like SAP
- Supports different languages such as English, Japanese, German, Spanish and French

MEGA

Powered by

<http://www.mega.fr/index.asp/l/en/c/solution>

It provides a set of products that supports EA, BPM, and Enterprise Risk Management.

Functionalities

- Supports modeling of EA
- Supports IT portfolio management
- Supports business process analysis
- Supports governance, risks, and compliance

Sparx Systems Enterprise Architect

Powered by

<http://www.sparxsystems.com.au/>

It provides a powerful UML tools for system development, project management, and object oriented CASE tools.

Functionalities

- Supports for Business requirement management, BPMN, business rules
- Supports for Software engineering, databases, and analyze legacy code
- Supports for Systems State chart modeling, and state machine code generation
- Supports for EA frameworks like TOGAF, DoDAF and Zackman

Qualiware

<http://www.qualiware.com/>

It provides a way for establishing graphical communication platform to involve the organizations employees through assigning tasks and activities.

Functionalities

- Supports EA, digital business, governance, risks, compliance, and BPM
- Supports delegation of tasks and activities.
- Supports personalized user interfaces according to user's preferences

Section 12: Enterprise Architecture Maturity

According to Gartner EA consulting firm the formal definition of EA maturity is “discipline for proactively and holistically leading enterprise responses to disruptive forces by identifying and analyzing the execution of change toward desired business vision and outcomes”. In more simple words, we can defined the EA maturity as the enterprise method of pre-identifying the disruptive out of hands changes and the wise decisions that will execute the necessary actions which will keep the enterprise operating toward the directions of its vision and goals.

EA maturity is a measurable factor that is assessed by measuring the measurements of the following criteria illustrated in the following figure:

- **EA Foundation:** is all about the tools used to describe the EA. It is measured by evaluating the efforts achieved to continuously improve the enterprise architecture. In addition, it is measured by evaluating to what extent the EA description is following the standards of modeling tools, techniques, and methodologies.
- **EA Development:** is all about the ways of applying what have been described about the EA using the right tools in the EA foundation. It is measured by evaluating the development ways compliance to the enterprise principles,

guidelines, and rules. Also, it is measured by evaluating how the enterprise current state has been assessed and the future state has been formulated. The most important is evaluating the transition architecture planning that will ensure the smooth transforming the enterprise to the desired future state.

- **EA Realization:** this criteria is exploited after the previous two criteria EA development and foundation are handled at high level of maturity. It is measured by evaluating to what extent the services or products are handled and operating in efficient way according the pre-formulated procedures. It is also measured by evaluating to what extent that business stakeholders or owner are aware about their responsibilities in the business processes and procedures of completing the services and products of the enterprise.
- **EA Alignment:** this criteria is where the business/IT alignment is evaluated and measured. The IT investment and technologies acquisition is must be aligned to the business strategy.

The EA maturity is important because of its significant impact to both enterprise complexity and performance as follows:

- **Enterprise Complexity:**
 - **People:** how the internal communications and politics are handled.
 - **Organizational Design:** how the level of management, roles fulfilment, and the operating markets/segments/countries are organized.
 - **Strategy:** how the changes in the strategy and the annual budgeting are formulated and processed formally.
 - **Products and Services:** how the enterprise is exploring new customers' demands and how it is launching new products or services.
 - **Processes:** how the enterprise is realizing the differences and significances of the core business and the support business processes.
 - **External:** how the enterprise is realizing the business competitors and the host countries laws and regulations.
- **Enterprise Performance:**
 - **IT costs:** how the enterprise is trying reduce the IT costs by decreasing the IT complexity and increasing the reuse.
 - **Customer Satisfaction:** how the enterprise is building good relationships with customers, improving the customers' services, and continuously seek their feedback to increase its services and products.

- **Operational Excellence:** how the enterprise is automating and optimizing the business environment with high level flexibility.
- **Decision Making:** how the enterprise is having correct information and easy visualization of the data available at anytime and anywhere.
- **Competitive Performance:** how the enterprise is continuously assessing the market shares. After that how it is reacting through agile strategies to enhance its position in the market or sustaining it.
- **Time to Market:** how the enterprise is planning the correct timing of introducing its services/products. Also, the agile development and services/ products lifecycle is important factor in this point.

The following figure illustrate the impact of EA maturity on the business complexity and further in the business performance:

Section 13: Enterprise Architecture Challenges

As mentioned earlier, EA is a powerful methodology to write an organization book of existence. However, a marvel hero once said “with great power, there must also come great responsibilities”. That means EA is facing many challenges and obstacles that has to be overcome in order to achieve the future state wished by organizations. Below is review of the most critical EA challenges the EA professionals are facing:

Unified, scientific, and practical EA definition

This is one of the major reasons that many organizations hesitate to conduct an EA initiative. The scientific society has not reached to a common accepted definition of EA worldwide. For example, there are many scientists who hypothesize EA as a methodology specialized for IT architecting, while others opposed this limitation of EA capabilities. In our humble opinion, we agree with the second saying which emphasized that EA is more than IT architecting and as mentioned we consider EA as a method of creating an enterprise book of existence.

Complexity from the World Openness

GLOBEs all around the world has still not having a full understanding of the globalization complexity impacts on their business sustaining. From strategic point of view, planning business in limited space or area is completely different from planning business with intention of running it globally. Therefore, EA is more complex to be conducted for long run and wide business.

Risks

One of the critical challenges for EA is to risks anticipation and reduction. EA is full decisions making in almost overall activities and such decision will highly affect the other dependencies. Therefore, EA is facing tremendous number of issues regarding the application and integrating risk management principles and best practices within the one smooth and comprehensive methodology.

Business requests repetition & insistence

Most of the time business stakeholders are repetitively requesting and insisting IT to simplify and fully automate some processes with minimal human intervention. In contrast, they are also requesting to have full alignment with governance policies and security matters that sometimes contradict and refuse the simplification and the minimization of human interventions. Such contradictions are valid in most of the

times to ensure the delegation of authorities, responsibilities, accountabilities, data integrity and corruption. Therefore, EA sometimes is put in enviable position when trying to find out a compromise in this matter.

Continuous emerging of technology

It is difficult and complex for EA to coordinate the rapid changes and fast emerging of various technologies. For example, in case of pervasive computing which will depend highly on the IoT internet of things technologies with many sensors for collecting and sending data, it is a key challenge to transfer the collected data into information and knowledge which is the essential of decision making.

Sustainable EA

One of the key challenges that EA is facing is keeping everything inline as the EA final design which will guarantee to reach the future desired state. Businesses sometimes go out the planned track when unexpected circumstances happened. Therefore, it not easy for EA to design a sustainable architecture for the enterprise when in some cases the business might include environmental or natural considerations as in green process management cases.

EA continuous assessment

EA complete design only will guarantee its actual success. Therefore, EA must be monitored, measured, assessed, and evaluated continuously. By doing this GOFs will ensure that they are getting the maximum benefits they can get after conducting the EA initiative and feel the real success. Determining the EA assessments criteria based on the nature of the enterprise is the actual challenge.

Ineffective EA leader or team

EA leader selecting and team formulating is considered as the key challenges that affect the overall success of the EA project.

Stakeholders understanding and commitment

This is a real challenge when the top management do not understand the criticality of the EA project and encouraging the employees to maximize their efforts in collaborating with the EA team and provide all the information they need.

Narrowing the EA concept to IT architecture

EA is more than IT architecture it includes all aspects of the enterprise.

Section 14: Enterprise Architecture & Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship formal definition is “the capacity and willingness to develop, organize, and manage a business venture along with any of its risks in order to make a profit”. In simple words, translating ideas to selling products or services. In complex words, it can be defined as the agile creation of a company from scratch that offers products or services from scratch walking through all the institutional processes including host-country procedures and licenses, location, recruitment, office equipping, materials supply, production lines, quality management, marketing, and sales.

What is the similarity between enterprise architects and entrepreneurs?

The similarities comes from that they share some common characteristics as follows:

- Having courage to take risks and go for new opportunities.
- Raising customers awareness
- Planning effective financial strategies and saving backup money to benefit hard situations.
- Focusing in the overall enterprise or company (linking all together).
- Moving easily from abstract strategy to details.
- Having knowledge about the subject business domain.
- Acquiring only the technology that serve directly the business goals.
- Understanding risks and prioritizing things.
- Multitasking
- Dealing with complexity using breakdown approach.

It is well known and worldwide agreed that gaining success is achievable only if the basics have been set by doing the right things right! And this is exactly what enterprise architects and entrepreneurs are doing.

If an entrepreneur has applied the methodologies of enterprise architecture, he/she will be more comfortable and relaxing in the future for their business growth and expanding.

Conclusion

This survey study has elaborated the main concepts of one the highly demanding field nowadays which is the EA (Enterprise Architecture). This field has been introduced to resolve the issues resulted out of money, time, and efforts wasting throughout the failed projects undertaken by organizations. Such wasting of resources happened most of the time due to the incomprehensive analysis and assessments of the overall requirements and needs across the entire organization. EA in very simple words is trying to build the organization using a top-bottom approach starting first with the analysis of the business layer which includes (vision, mission, strategies, goals, objectives, and processes). Second, the analysis of the organization's systems and applications derived and serve the business layer. Third, the analysis of organization's data that will be processed and generated by the second layer. At last, it ends up with the analysis and design of the IT infrastructure layer. The survey covers all the EA important aspects for new interested professionals and it is considered as a good starting point. Most importantly, the study has shown the basics of some common EA frameworks such as Zhackman, TOGAF, Oracle EAF, FEAF, and Gartner. It is also conducted a comparison between these frameworks. Additionally, many EA tools that help the EA architects or the EA team in general in conducting the EA project successfully. Finally, it is highly recommended as a future work is to enrich this survey study with a practical case study and implement its enterprise architecture using the principles of the one of the frameworks and practicing the designs and documentations in one of the EA tools.

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